

SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENTS

Supplementary Document 4. Figure III. Daily PM_{2.5} concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) recorded at the “Las Encinas Monitoring Station” (Temuco, Chile) during the study period (January 1 to September 30, 2021). PM_{2.5} levels were measured externally using a beta attenuation monitor BAM 1020 (Met One Instruments, Inc., Grant Pass, OR, USA), equipped with a carbon-14 ($60 \mu\text{Ci} \pm 15 \mu\text{Ci}$) beta source and a photomultiplier tube beta detector with an organic plastic scintillator, operating at a flow rate of 16.7 L/min. Data were provided by “Algoritmos y Mediciones Ambientales SpA” and accessed via the National Air Quality Information System (<https://sinca.mma.gob.cl>). The chart differentiates between validated (blue), preliminary (orange), and unvalidated (green) records.